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Working paper

The design of a tool for the measurement of occupations in websurveys using a global index of occupations

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Abstract

Occupation is a key variable in socio-economic research, used in a wide variety of studies, but the measurement of occupations is a major challenge. In case of open-ended survey questions, websurveys pose extra challenges, as respondents are more likely to key in odd text compared to other survey modes, particularly those with an interviewer. Websurveys however offer new opportunities for closed survey questions with self-identification of occupations, particularly when using semantic matching and a database with large numbers of coded occupational titles. This paper details the design requirements for such a database to facilitate surveys in multiple countries.

First, this paper describes how the WISCO Database of Occupations has developed since its first use in 2000, when the database was applied in the WageIndicator websurvey on work and wages. By the end of 2015 the websurvey and the database had expanded to 85 countries. In these fifteen years, the number of occupations in the database had increased from 55 to 1,896 and the languages covered from 1 to 43.

The paper then presents an overview of the ISCO occupational classification with four hierarchical levels and their coding. It also reviews how occupations can be measured in websurveys in open-ended or closed survey questions. For the closed question three approaches are detailed, notably scrolling, search trees and semantic matching. Given that any national labour market easily cover 10,000 or more occupational titles, the semantic matching is considered the best approach provided that the look-up tables include 5,000 or more occupational titles for each country.

Finally, the paper details the design principles in the database used for semantic matching. It discusses the size of the source list in relation to the ISCO coding. It details the issue of male and female titles and the use of start or end years for occupations. It specifies how the database copes with highly aggregated occupational titles such as clerk or manager, with abbreviations and organisation specific job titles, with synonyms, with skill levels within and across occupations, with occupations in the corporate hierarchy, with composite jobs, with handicraft workers, and with subsistence farmers and hunters. Next, it details how to cope with respondents indicating that their job title is not in the database.

The paper ends with a future outlook for a programme to test the validity and reliability of occupational measurement.

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1. Introduction

Occupation is a key variable in socio-economic research, used in a wide variety of studies. Where such studies use quantitative approaches, they usually rely on survey data. Measuring and coding of occupations is a major challenge for socio-economic surveys. Websurveys pose extra challenges, as is the main focus of this paper.

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Within WP21 this paper addresses specifically Task 21.1.3 'Develop methods to facilitate the EU-wide measurement of occupations in websurveys'. This paper builds on a paper already finished for WP21, notably the InGRID working paper 'Reviewing the measurement and comparison of occupations across Europe' (Tijdens, 2014b).² These papers also build on discussions in the InGRID expert workshop 'Developing and testing new tools to measure occupations and their task and skill requirements', held 10-12 February 2014 in Amsterdam.³

This paper details the design principles in the WISCO Database of Occupations_v2016. In Section 2 the history of the database is sketched. Section 3 provides an overview of the measurement and coding of occupations. Section 4 specifies the design for an occupations look-up table for semantic matching. Section 5 outlines further steps to be taken for the development of a database facilitating the EU-wide measurement of occupations in websurveys using an Application Programming Interface (API).

1 See page 54-55 of Annex I - 'Description of Work' for Project InGRID Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion, funded from EU's Framework Programme 7, INFRA-2012-1.1.1. Research infrastructures for the study of poverty, working life and living conditions, Grant agreement no. 312691.

2 See <https://inclusivegrowth.be/downloads/output/m21-2-working-paper-measurement-kea-tijdens.pdf>, accessed 17-12-2015.

3 See <https://inclusivegrowth.be/events/call6-ExpertWorkshop>, accessed 17-12-2015.

2. The history of the WISCO database of occupations

2.1 The start in 2000

In 2000, WageIndicator started in the Netherlands, aiming to collect up-to-date information about women's wage data by occupation. Hence, large sample sizes were needed. A volunteer survey was published in several women's magazines, resulting in almost 7,000 completed questionnaires. At the same time the survey was posted on a well-known women's website, resulting in more than 7,000 questionnaires. In the print survey the 55 most frequent occupations were listed, clustered into seven groups with an option 'other' at the bottom of each group. The reasons for the choice in favour of a predefined list instead of a text box were related to the data-entry costs. In the websurvey, this list took the form of 2-level search tree, including an option 'other' which was followed by an open text. Slightly over one quarter of the respondents used the text box to enter a job title not listed, which were recoded into 19 additional occupational titles (Tijdens, 2001).

In 2001, WageIndicator started its own website, presenting a Salary Check for women, based on the survey data. The websurvey was posted on the website and visitors were invited to complete the survey, which was now addressing both women and men. For the occupation question, a two level search listing the most frequent occupations for men as well as the 55 plus the 19 additional women's occupations, resulting in 105 occupational titles (Tijdens *et al*, 2002). These titles were coded according to the Standard Occupational Classification from Statistics Netherlands.

2.2 The WOLIWEB and EurOccupations projects

In 2004, as part of the EU-funded WOLIWEB project (EU-FP6, no. 506590), WageIndicator could start websites with continuous websurveys on work and wages in another seven countries, at that time the largest in the European Union. Again the choice was in favour of a predefined list with a search tree and not in favour of post-coding text strings, due to budgetary considerations. To populate the list of occupations, project partners were asked to send coding indexes or other lists of occupations from their countries, and preferably provide an English translation of the titles. The list of English titles was named the source list. By 2006, the database contained in total more than 5,000 occupational titles, many of them present in one language and in English. Occupations from different countries with the same English occupational title were merged. For most countries the database included a list of 500 to 1500 occupations. The aggregation level of the occupational titles varied across the countries, including both very broad and very narrow titles. Where possible, the titles in the source list were coded ISCO-88, otherwise they received a follow-up number. In 2005 and 2006, some countries added occupational titles to the list, based on feedback from web visitors who could not identify their occupation. The search tree in the websurvey was extended from 2 to 3 levels.

In 2006, the EurOccupations project (EU-FP6, no. 028987) allowed to adapt and modify the database. Based on Draft 3 of ISCO-08, published in September 2006 (ILO, 2006), and on ILO's alphabetical index of occupational titles for ISCO-88(COM), the source list was revised and coded according ISCO-08. This resulted in a source list with 1433 occupational titles. Hence, the list held occupational titles at the 5-digit level of the ISCO-08 classification. If translations were not available in the database, the occupations were translated for the languages of the eight EU countries in the project.

Since 2007/Q2, the list was implemented in the WageIndicator websurvey, using a three level search tree. In spring 2008, ILO published the final draft ISCO-08 classification with 433 occupational titles at 4-digit level.⁴ Compared to Draft 3, a number of occupations was assigned a different skill level. The codes in our source list of occupations were adapted accordingly. Meanwhile, the WageIndicator partners in non-EurOccupations countries had commented the source list, noticing translation difficulties and adding missing occupational titles. The source list was extended and critically reviewed with regard to internal consistency and suitability within the search tree of the websurvey. Early 2009, the source list included 1,594 distinct occupational titles with translations for approximately 30 languages for almost 50 countries in and outside Europe. The database was renamed the World Database of ISCO Occupations (WISCO). The primary aim of the WISCO Database of Occupations was its use for valid self-identification of occupation in websurveys by means of a search tree (Tijdens, 2010).

2.3 The search tree and semantic matching

In 2009, the revised WISCO Database of Occupations was uploaded in the WageIndicator websurvey for all countries. Data collection started for some countries as of July 2009, but for most countries as of October 2009. The database and the search tree were also implemented in the Salary Checks in most of the 50 countries with a WageIndicator website at that time. With millions of web visitors and over a hundred thousand respondents per year, the search tree and the occupation database were tested extensively. Web visitors and survey respondents send relatively few emails to WageIndicator about the occupations, pointing to a satisfactory search tree and the related list of occupations.

In the years after 2009, occupations have been added to the database, mostly because web visitors requested so in their emails. For the UK, a number of management occupations and for the Czech Republic and Slovakia medical specialists have been added and for Germany the skill levels for some skilled occupations have been further detailed by distinguishing occupations at university and higher vocational level. By 2015, the database held between 1,896 occupational titles, of which 132 were country specific. Apart from the latter 132, almost all titles were translated in the 43 languages of the WageIndicator websites and websurveys. The number of occupational titles varied slightly across countries, because in some countries some occupation titles could not be translated or distinct occupational titles in the source list were translated similarly. Figure 2.1 shows a cut out of the database.

4 The final ISCO-08 coding index was published in 2012 (ILO, 2012).

Figure 2.1 Screenshot of the 2015 WISCO database of occupations

1	ISCO0813	Master label	am_ET	ar	az_AZ	ba_ID
2	110010000000	Commissioned officer armed forces	የአር ያይሎች ባለጥገር ጦሮች	ضابط في القوات المسلحة	Harbi qüvvələrin zabiti	Perwira angkatan darat
3	110020000000	Military operations leader	የጦር ስራዎች ማሰር	رئيس العمليات العسكرية	Harbi amaliyyatların rəhbəri	Pimpinan operasi militer
4	111101000000	Member of parliament, legislator	የፓርላማ አባል የሥነ ሕግ ሰነድ	عضو في البرلمان ، مشرع	Parlament üzvü	Pembuat undang-undang
5	111102000000	Mayor, alderman		عمدة ، رئيس مجلس بلدي	Mer, icra hakimiyyətinin rəhbəri	Mayor, anggota dewan kota
6	111113000000	City councillor, county councillor	የከተማ ምክር ቤት አባል የኮንቲ ቤት	عضو مجلس محلي أو القروي / بلدية	Şəhər şura üzvü, Region şurası	Anggota dewan kota
7	111202000000	Public administration manager	የአገልግሎት አገልግሎት ማሰር	مدير الدائرة العامة	Administrasiya rəisi, dövlət xidməti rəhbəri	Manajer administrasi publik
8	111203000000	Senior non-legislative official	ከፍተኛ ሥነ ሕግ ሰነድ ስራ ማሰር	كبار المسؤولين الحكوميين من غير	Qeyri-dövlət müəssisəsinin işçisi	Pejabat senior bukan pembuat
9	111204000000	Senior government official	ከፍተኛ የጥገና ሰነድ ስራ ማሰር	مسؤول حكومي كبير	Dövlət müəssisəsinin işçisi	Pejabat senior pemerintahan
10	111206000000	Diplomat	ዲፕሎማት	دبلوماسي	Diplomat	Diplomat
11	111301000000	Traditional chief or head of village	ባላላዊ ሊቀ ወይም የጥገና ሰነድ	عمدة أو رئيس القرية	Kənd sovetinin nümayəndəsi	Kepala kampung/suku
12	111401000000	Employers' organisation official	የጥገና ሰነድ ስራ ማሰር	مسؤول منظمة أرباب العمل	Mağşulluq xidməti nümayəndəsi	Pejabat senior organisasi peng
13	111402000000	Humanitarian organisation official	የሰነድ ስራ ማሰር	مسؤول منظمة إنسانية	Humanitar yardım təşkilatı nümayəndəsi	Pejabat senior organisasi kema
14	111403000000	Political party official	የፖለቲካ ፓርቲ ስራ ማሰር	مسؤول الأحزاب السياسية	Siyasi partiya nümayəndəsi	Pejabat senior partai politik

Note The first column shows the ISCO-08 code (first 4-digits are the ISCO code); the second column shows the source label, the remaining columns show the translations for Amharic, Arabic, Azeri and Indonesian.

In 2012, the search tree in the websurvey and the Salary Check was extended with a semantic matching tool (Figure 2.2). Semantic matching allows visitors to self-identify their occupation by typing text whereby matches with words in the list of occupations for their particular language are instantly shown. Visitors can then select the most relevant match. The 2015 websurvey data shows that nine in ten respondents use the semantic matching.

Figure 2.2 Screenshot for the tool to self-identify occupation with a search tree and with semantic matching

Source WageIndicator Salary Check for Great Britain, <http://wageindicator.co.uk/main/pay/salarycheck>, accessed 15-12-2015

Although 1,600 occupational titles may seem a large number, one has to take into account that a labour market in any country can easily include 10,000 or more job titles. The use of the database for self-identification in websurveys would therefore profit from extending the number of occupations as well as from further testing of the database. In 2014, the InGRID project provided funding for the design of a tool for the measurement of occupations in websurveys using a global index of occupations. In 2015, the SERISS project (EU-Horizon 2020, no. 654221) provided funding to populate the database, according to the design principles outlined here, to 5,000 titles and to more countries/languages, and to develop an Application programming interface (API) for the measurement of occupations in websurveys.

3. Overview: classifying and measuring occupations

3.1 Classifying occupations

3.1.1 Occupational classifications

In 1958, the International Labour Office (ILO) of the United Nations had developed the International Standard of Occupational Classification (ISCO) to harmonise the measurement of occupations, with revisions in 1968, 1988, and 2008. Today, ISCO has become the standard classification in many countries for their Labour Force Surveys or Censuses. ISCO-08, as was the case for its predecessors, defines a job as a set of work tasks and duties performed by one person. Jobs with the same set of main tasks and duties are aggregated into the so-called 4-digit occupation units. On the basis of similarity in the tasks and duties performed, the units are grouped into 3- and 2-digit groups, which in turn on the basis of the skill level are grouped into 1-digit groups (Hunter, 2014). ISCO distinguishes four skill levels, notably unskilled, semi-skilled, skilled and highly skilled, which are related to ISCED, the International Standard Classification of Education (ILO, 2012).

3.1.2 Classifying occupations in a multi-country approach

ILO's ISCO classification and coding index assume that occupations with the same titles are classified similarly across countries, otherwise there would not be an argument for a global classification. Hence, the database of occupations challenges whether occupations with the same title are similar across countries. This applies to same languages in different countries, but even more so to different languages in different countries. The answer is that we don't know and that we have neither the methods nor the means to test empirically whether the statement is true. Within the EurOccupations project as well as in the Eduworks and Ingrid projects empirical tests have been undertaken to measure the heterogeneity of tasks within occupations (Tijdens, De Ruijter, De Ruijter, 2012; Tijdens, De Ruijter, De Ruijter, 2014; Visintin *et al.*, 2015). The results show that the frequencies of a given set of tasks within each occupation vary largely within and across countries. This challenges research of occupational boundaries within and across countries, but such studies are beyond the scope of this paper.

ISCO-08 defines a 4-digit classification for worldwide use and is available in English. Following its policy towards a harmonised occupational classification, the European Commission (2009) has translated the ISCO 4-digit classification into all languages of the European Union to ensure that occupations are coded similarly across countries.⁵ When it comes to classifying 5-digit occupations however, two approaches can be distinguished. The first one says that the ILO manual and descriptions are sufficiently detailed and hence it is assumed that national coding of 5-digit occupations leads to valid results across countries. This method is applied in many multi-country surveys, where the field organisations code the occupations for their respective countries. The second approach states that only English occupational titles should be coded, and that therefore national job titles should be translated and then coded according to the English title. For three countries (Albania, Kosovo & Montenegro) this method is followed for EuroFound's European Working Conditions Survey 2010

5 See http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=urisrv:OJ.L_2009.292.01.0031.01.ENG, accessed 8 Augustus 2014.

WCS: the verbatim responses were translated in English to facilitate central quality control (Gallup Europe, 2010). In retrospect Ganzeboom (2014), applying the first approach in his effort to code parental occupations in the European Social Survey, acknowledges that it would have been much better to ask the coders to translate the occupation titles in English and then code these. Ganzeboom states that particularly because Google Translate has become a big help in this respect. It is not sure which approach is less costly. In the first approach the costs are related to the national coding, while no multi-country quality control can be applied. In the second approach translations might be costly, but central coding of the English occupations for the entire multi-country data collection is relatively cheap. In this proposal for a multi-country occupational coding tool, the second approach will be followed and all occupational titles will be translated in English.

3.1.3 Coding occupations

Many statistical offices and survey agencies have developed coding indexes and related coding tools to facilitate office coding of the raw text from an open ended survey question about respondent's occupation. A well-known coding tool is CASCOT, an abbreviation of Computer Assisted Structured Coding Tool. CASCOT is a computer programme designed to make the coding of text information to standard classifications simpler, quicker and more reliable. It is developed and maintained by the Warwick Institute for Employment Research of the University of Warwick in Great Britain. CASCOT is available for coding occupations in nine languages, notably Dutch, English, Finnish, French, German, Italian, Portuguese, Slovak, and Spanish.⁶ In the USA and in Germany auto-coders are developed (Cheeseman Day, 2014; Bethmann *et al.*, 2014). A huge training set of coded responses is required to apply machine learning algorithms.

These tools for office coding consist of an index for coding the verbatim responses plus a set of rules, that indicate which phrases are redundant, for example the words 'I work as a'. The rules also may identify the most common typing errors, may remove other superfluous or irrelevant text, and apply extra checks for aggregated or vague occupations. CASCOT and the auto-coders can identify to what extent the raw text matches an occupational title in the coding index. For automatic coding, for example in CASCOT, the thresholds of 80 or 70% can be set to accept the match as a valid code.

3.2 Measuring occupations in websurveys

3.2.1 Open versus closed questions in websurveys

Websurveys challenge the measurement of occupations. As in other survey modes, an open question can be applied. It is likely however that the response is less reliable than in other survey modes. In contrast to other surveys modes, an interviewer cannot correct odd responses. In addition, websurveys elicit more often odd responses than I've noticed in printed surveys. In the anonymity of the Internet, responses such as 'None of your business' and worse are given. Compared to other survey modes, websurveys however allow for self-identification using extensive look-up tables. Surveys with a mixed mode approach face difficult choices here, but surveys that are solely based on the web mode can explore the look-up tables. Note that both websurveys and self-identification assume respondents' reading skills and therefore poses high demands on readability of the look-up tables.

Websurveys allow for self-identification using a look-up database. This database however needs contain a large number of entries to satisfy the large majority of respondents, given labour markets of 10,000 or more occupational titles and given a skewed distribution of jobholders over occupations.

⁶ See <http://www2.warwick.ac.uk/fac/soc/ier/software/cascot/internet/>, accessed 17-12-2015.

The content of the database will be discussed in the Section 4. In websurveys, three techniques facilitate searching a look-up table. First, an alphabetically sorted drop-down list can be used. Second, a search tree with two or three levels can be used. Third, an open format question with semantic matching can be used. All three will be discussed hereafter.

'Don't know' answers are rarely given to the question about occupation and therefore I assume that almost all respondents know their job title. They tend to report a detailed job title, as they know it from their employment contract, job classification scheme, collective bargaining agreement, job advertisement, or just from a common understanding in the workplace. Moreover, respondents are able to aggregate their job title in an occupational title, if different from the job title, because the occupational title is used in labour market communication, for example in educational trajectories or job ads. Hence, once presented a list of occupational titles, respondents will recognise that their occupational title is asked and not their job title, and they will be able to aggregate their job title into their occupational title.

3.2.2 Scrolling

Scrolling is typically applied to exhaustive tables that contain well defined and general understood words. Scrolling assumes that these words can be sorted alphabetically in a commonly understood way. Due to readability considerations scrolling requires a database with not too many entries, typically at most a few hundred entries. A list of countries can be searched perfectly by means of an alphabetically sorted scroll list, allowing web visitors to easily identify their country of choice from a list of approximately 250 items. Couper presents another example, notably a list of drugs (Couper *et al.*, 2012).

Can scrolling be applied for self-identification of occupation? Occupational titles are not standardised and hence the occupational titles air-conditioning mechanic and mechanic air-conditioning are used interchangeably. For the alphabetic sorting in a scroll list however this requires multiple entries for ne occupational titles. Given that the look-up table preferably holds thousands of entries, the requirement of multiple entries enlarges the table substantially. Therefore, it must be concluded that scrolling is not an appropriate technique for respondent's self-identification of occupation in websurveys.

3.2.3 Search trees

A search tree or an 'iPod menu', as it is sometimes called, allows visitors to navigate through a look-up table. Typically a search tree is used for nested items, such as cities within provinces, whereby only one search path leads to a city. Search trees commonly have two levels, but can have three. Each level within the search tree preferably should be sorted alphabetically to facilitate respondents' understanding of the tree. Additionally, a search tree requires that the parent entries are phrased in a commonly understood, unambiguous way. Note that, although the ISCO classification is a hierarchical system, it is designed for classification purposes and not for the purpose of self-identification. Hence, the classification does not provide the content for a search tree.

When the WageIndicator websurvey started in 2001, the survey used a search tree for the self-identification of occupation, as explained in Section 2. For such self-identification a search tree was the only possibility, because at that time the semantic matching technique was not available for websurveys. Moreover, web visitors used a desktop to visit the website and to complete the survey. For reasons of readability on a desktop screen, the number of entries in each level of the search tree was maximised to at most 20 entries, and hence the total number of entries in the look-up table was maximised with at most 20 entries in the 1st level, $20 \times 20 = 400$ entries in the 2nd level and $20 \times 20 \times 20 = 8,000$ entries in the 3rd level. Given that quite some occupational titles had to be placed on more than one search path, the total number of entries was much lower. In 2001, the look-up

table in the Netherlands comprised of less than 400 occupational titles, and therefore the search tree could cope with 2 levels. In the following years the number of occupations grew and the search tree had to be expanded to three levels.

For respondents it is cognitive demanding and time consuming to navigate through such an extensive search tree, and does therefore result in partial drop out (Tijdens, 2014a). To find a solution for the dilemma between the growing number of occupational titles in the database and the need to reduce the number of entries in the search tree, occupations with presumably few jobholders were not included, although an empirical underpinning of the distribution of jobholders over a 5-digit occupations was lacking. Additionally, to reduce entries similar occupational titles were merged into one entry in the 3rd level, because the search path was the same for similar job titles and respondents would recognise similar occupational titles as their own. Third level entries included occupational titles such as:

- carpenter, joiner;
- goldsmith, silversmith;
- city councillor, county councillor;
- clown, acrobat, magician, hypnotist.

3.2.4 Semantic matching

Semantic matching is typically applied in cases where the list of items is not exhaustive and the phrasing of the search term is fuzzy. Google Search is a well-known example of searching with semantic matching. For self-identification of occupations, semantic matching is probably the best solution, but it requires an exhaustive look-up list in order to provide matches for the vast majority of respondents. Hence, the look-up table used in the search tree should be extended and the merged occupational titles should be unmerged into one entry per occupational title. Section 4 explains the underlying principles used for the source list.

Google Search can cope with typing errors by suggesting ‘Do you mean xxx?’. Currently the semantic matching tool in the WageIndicator websurvey cannot cope with typing errors, as Figure 3.1 shows. I assume that respondents will correct their text when no matches show up, or that they will use the search tree. It may well be the case that in the foreseeable future the tool can provide suggestions, but this will not be implemented in this stage.

Figure 3.1 Screenshot showing that a typing error does not provide a match

Source WageIndicator Salary Check for Great Britain, <http://wageindicator.co.uk/main/pay/salarycheck>, accessed 15-12-2015

3.2.5 The activities and duties question

In an overview of 25 surveys with an open-ended question about occupation, 14 ask for a job description (Tijdens, 2014). This is the so-called tasks-and-duties-question, and is typically asked for office coding purposes, notably when the answer to the occupation question cannot be coded. The phrasing of the question varied largely across the surveys.

From winter 2015 onwards, the WageIndicator websurvey respondents are asked to provide a description of their job. Respondents are asked so after having identified their 5-digit occupation with the semantic matching tool. The tasks-and-duties responses will be used to identify the reliability of the selected 5-digit occupation.

4. Design requirements of a database for semantic matching

4.1 Introduction

This section details the design requirements for a database to facilitate respondents' self-identification of occupation by means of semantic matching in websurveys.⁷ It discusses the principles underlying the design of the database, including a review of problems to be solved. Table 4.1 presents the main concepts used in this section.

Table 4.1 The main concepts used in this section

Source list	The list of all occupations in the database, in English
Code	The ISCO-08 codes of the source list
Locale	The combination of language and country, for example en_US and es_US
Translation	The translation of an occupational title in the source list to the language of the respective locale
Look-up table	The list shown to the survey respondent, depending of the locale of the survey
Database	The joint source list, codes and translations
Entry	One occupational title in a look-up table

A coding tool for office coding is typically designed for high volume batch coding and providing a certainty score per coded verbatim. For a semantic matching tool in websurveys, this application is irrelevant. Here, the purpose of the database is to provide each respondent with a list of matches for a choice of his/her most relevant occupational title. The database aims to generate responses at 4-digit level of the ISCO-08 classification and to prevent responses at 1-, 2-, or 3-digit level and to prevent unidentifiable responses.

4.2 Drafting and coding the source list

4.2.1 The size of the source list

Given that a national labour market easily can consist of 10,000 or more occupational titles and given that the distribution of jobholders over these occupational titles is extremely skewed, it will be impossible to draft an exhaustive database of all occupational titles. For an open-ended survey question with office coding this implies that every survey includes respondents in rare occupations which have not been reported and hence not coded in previous surveys. In case of self-identification with semantic matching these respondents probably will try the titles of adjacent occupations. Nevertheless, to meet the demand the source list should include as many occupations as possible.

⁷ The database may also serve for interviewer identification of respondents' occupations in computer-assisted personal face-to-face (CAPI) and computer-assisted telephone (CATI) survey modes. This is predominantly a technical challenge and therefore beyond the scope of this paper. For the postal (PAPI) mode no other method than an open ended survey question is available, because this mode is not computer-assisted.

As discussed in Section 2, for a websurvey with self-identification by means of a search tree the number of occupational titles in the source list is limited, but this technical constraint does not hold for semantic matching. Hence, the source list can be very large. Given time and budget restrictions however, we decided to depart from the ISCO-08 coding index with almost 7,000 occupational titles (ILO 2012). This database includes however duplicate titles.⁸

4.2.2 The drafting of the source list – first step

A two-step procedure will be followed for the design of the source list. In a first step only 5-digit occupational titles with reliable ISCO-08 coding will be included. These are found in three sources:

1. the more than 6,000 occupational titles in the ISCO-08 Index EN May 2013 final draftAW coding index, controlled for duplicates (English only);
2. the more than 1,700 occupational titles of the WISCO database (English + translations);
3. the occupational titles in the ISCO-08 coding indexes of 18 national statistical offices in not-English speaking countries.⁹ These coding indexes are in national languages and will be translated to English, using Google Translate and checked by a skilled translator. Typically coding indexes apply reverse word order, to facilitate office coding. For inclusion in the database the words will be changed into the right order.

In a next step, all English occupational titles will be checked for duplicates. Hence, if an occupation from the Spanish and one from the Latvian indexes are translated to the same English occupational title, they will be one title in the source list with the same ISCO-08 code. If this occupational title is not present in the coding indexes of the other countries, it will be translated to the respective languages. To increase the comparability of occupations across countries, translations by national labour market experts are preferred over translations by professional translators, and national used occupational titles are preferred over literal translations. Note that even in countries with the same language the same occupations may have different titles. Therefore, each locale has its own look-up table.

Once all above mentioned lists are entered in the database, the coding needs to be checked for consistency. For example, if the occupations from the Spanish and the Latvian indexes are translated in the same English occupational title, but have been coded differently by the Spanish respectively Latvian statistical office, a final check is required. Either a translation is not correct and therefore should not be considered the same occupation, or the same occupation was coded differently in any of the coding indexes. Hence, the translations and the codes should be checked. For the latter we propose to use the CASCOT coding tool to decide about the code.

4.2.3 The drafting of the source list – second step

Once the database drafted in the first step is satisfactory, other lists of occupations from non-English speaking countries will be considered for adding to the database. These may be lists with or without an ISCO-08 code. If an occupation from a list is not yet present in the look-up table of the country at stake, it will be translated in English and checked if adding the occupation makes sense. Among others, the following lists will be considered:

1. the database of licensed occupations in the European Union;
2. the database of occupations included in the WageIndicator Collective Agreements Database and Minimum Wage Database in Africa, Asia and Latin America;
3. a database of 300 occupations which were translated from English in several Slavic languages
4. the ESCO occupation database;

⁸ Note that the SERISS project aimed to enlarge the database to 5,000 titles.

⁹ Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovak Republic, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Turkey.

5. a file with translated university positions;
6. lists of occupations for languages not yet available from the coding indexes such as Japanese or Arabic.

The resulting source list may include more than 7,000 occupational titles, and each look-up table will probably include 4,000 or more titles. Note that it occurs regularly that two distinct titles in English are translated to one title in a foreign language, thereby reducing the size of the look-up table for that language.

4.2.4 ISCO-08 occupations 'not elsewhere classified'

To ensure high quality coding, for each locale its look-up table of course needs to include at least one 5-digit occupational title in each ISCO-08 4-digit occupational unit. However, in case of office coding unidentifiable occupations are usually classified in the appropriate residual 4-digit occupational category, called 'not elsewhere classified', for example Unit Group 1349 'Professional Services Managers Not Elsewhere Classified'. ISCO-08 4-digit has 27 residual units. Luckily, ILO (2012) lists examples of occupational titles classified in the residual units. The database includes these occupational titles, and hence all ISCO-08 4-digit units have at least one entry in the source list and in the look-up tables.

4.3 Male versus female titles

In some countries male and female occupational titles are different, whereas in other countries only gender-neutral or male occupational titles are in use. For example for Germany, the English word DTP operator is translated to DTP Operator for men and DTP Operatorin for women. The vast majority of German occupational titles have distinct words for males and females. Even in English, a few female and male occupational titles are distinguished, for example actor and actress or waiter and waitress. In a search tree, for readability reasons the occupational titles should be brief and easy to understand, and therefore feminine occupational titles had to be restricted to a minimum. In the semantic matching database, however, it is easy to include a so-called gender filter and the look-up table should include columns for male and female occupational titles. Hence, the look-up table does not include an occupation Watchman/woman, but a male occupation Watchman and a female occupation Watchwoman. If the respondent's gender is female, the matching results from the female column will be shown, if present. Otherwise, the male/neutral titles from the look-up table will be shown. If the respondent's gender is not known, the male titles will be shown.

4.4 Start year and end year

Occupational structures are dynamic and the occupational composition of a labour force varies over time and across countries. Due to technological and organisational changes, new and emerging occupations arise. Most surveys ask respondents for their current occupation, but some have questions about father's and mother's occupation, mostly specified as the occupation when respondent was 14 years of age. Other surveys address elderly people, who are no longer in paid employment, but are asked to report their last occupation before retirement. This challenges the identification of time frames for the occupational titles. A straddle carrier driver or a web manager did not exist in periods when the straddle carrier or the web was not yet introduced. Therefore a start year can be assigned to an occupation in the source list. Hence, start years do not vary across countries. Of course, start years are only assigned to those occupations where this is known, for example in the case of web managers, where the start year 1985 is assigned.

The dynamic occupational structure also points to obsolete occupations, challenging the assignment of an end year to occupations in the look-up table. The database of historical occupations

HISCO does include occupational titles that don't exist today, because the machinery, equipment or materials used have become outdated. The HISCO scheme is based on the coding of the 1,000 most frequent male and female occupational titles in datasets from eight different countries: Belgium, Britain, Canada, France, Germany, the Netherlands, Norway and Sweden.¹⁰ The occupational data which were employed to develop the scheme span the period 1690-1970, but are mostly from the nineteenth century. The HISCO database is not intended to be included in the look-up table, but whenever a need arises to do so, it could easily be done. Whenever an occupation in the database is obviously outdated, an end year will be assigned.

4.5 Highly aggregated job titles: clerks, operators or teachers

From office coding it is well-known that some respondents tend to report a highly aggregated job title such as clerk, operator or teacher. These titles are too aggregated to be classified at a 4-digit level. Typically, surveys with open text field provide instructions to prevent this problem. In the database, these highly aggregated occupational titles are therefore not included. If respondents key in 'teacher', they are offered a choice of many teaching occupations, and similarly when they key in 'clerk', as Figure 4.1 shows. Similarly, no entries for highly aggregated occupational titles such as 'manager' or 'shopkeeper'. The database holds only specific titles.

Figure 4.1 Screenshot showing the match list for highly aggregated occupations

Source WageIndicator Salary Check for Great Britain, <http://wageindicator.co.uk/main/pay/salarycheck>, accessed 15-12-2015

4.6 Abbreviations and organisation specific job titles

In work organisations, people may use abbreviations or very specific words for their job title. As it is impossible to trace these abbreviated job titles across countries, the database does not include these very specific job titles. They do not provide a match, challenging the respondent to key in a related occupational title, as Figure 4.2 shows.

¹⁰ See <https://socialhistory.org/en/projects/hisco-history-work>, accessed 15-12-2015.

Figure 4.2 Screenshot showing that an abbreviation does not provide a match

Source WageIndicator Salary Check for Great Britain, <http://wageindicator.co.uk/main/pay/salarycheck>, accessed 15-12-2015

4.7 Synonyms

Some occupations have one or more synonym titles. As much as possible, these titles will be included in the look-up tables, because survey respondents may search on either synonym. For example, the occupations barber, hairdresser, and hairstylist are all included in the English look-up table for the United Kingdom. In other countries, the three occupational titles would possibly be translated to one title. In those cases they are only once present in that look-up table and they are assigned the 5-digit code of the most generic term of the synonyms. Synonym occupational titles will have different 5-digit codes, but the same 4-digit code. Note that a look-up table for semantic matching cannot assign two different codes to the same occupational title. Hence, for each language the look-up table consists of unique titles only. Some occupational titles can be written in reverse order. An example is *Cleaner aircraft* and *Aircraft cleaner*. In case of semantic matching both ways facilitate matching. In these cases the look-up tables will therefore include one entry only.

One could consider slang words for occupations as synonyms. For example the word wig picker is slang for psychiatrist. However, slang words are not included in the database and respondents will not be provided with a match, as Figure 4.3 shows. These respondents will understand that they need to enter another word or use the search tree.

Figure 4.3 Screenshot showing that a slang word does not provide a match

Source WageIndicator Salary Check for Great Britain, <http://wageindicator.co.uk/main/pay/salarycheck>, accessed 15-12-2015

4.8 Skill levels, professionals, associate professionals and certified occupations

ISCO-08 distinguishes four skill levels, referring to the ISCED educational categories (ILO 2012). An occupation's required skill level is the basis of ISCO's skill level structure. This challenges measurement difficult issues that have to be solved in the source list of the database, as will be discussed here.

A first issue is that ISCO uses the words professional and associate professional to distinguish between the highly skilled and the skilled professionals. Using the semantic matching respondents will definitely not use these words to indicate their occupation. This challenges the source list to phrase occupational titles such that respondents will assess their appropriate skill level. For example, the word engineer is used only for highly skilled occupations, the word technician is used for skilled

occupations and the word mechanic for semi-skilled. But even if these words are replaced by more commonly understood occupational titles, how will a respondent select between a Ship engineering technician (major group 3) and a Ship engineer (major group 2), because they both provide a match on the search term ‘ship engineer’? One solution can be to default classify these occupations in major group 3 and add a follow-up question about the occupation’s required educational level according to the ISCED classification to decide whether the respondent should be classified in major group 2.

Another solution is to include a reference to the required education. In the Netherlands, for example, the associate nurse is distinguished from the professional nurse because the occupational title includes a reference to the required education, notably ‘*verpleegkundige (mbo)*’ and ‘*verpleegkundige (hbo)*’ [nurse with medium vocational training and nurse with higher vocational training]. In Belgium, as learned from the EurOccupations expert, only one nurse occupation does exist. Therefore, the look-up table will not include an occupation title for the Nursing associate professional. Of course, this approach is based on country-level information, which obviously will not be available for all countries at stake. In these cases the database will include the translated occupational titles.

Table 4.2 Code, source list and two look-up tables for two occupational titles

Code	Source list	nl_NL	nl_BE
22210100	Hospital nurse	Verpleegkundige (hbo)	Verpleegkundige
32210100	Nursing associate professional	Verpleegkundige (mbo)	-

A second issues relates to the fact that within countries and within ISCO skill levels, occupations can refer to distinct ISCED levels. In Germany, for example, the ‘*Archivar/in, Diplom (FH)*’ is distinct from the ‘*Archivar/in, Diplom (Uni)*’ [Archivist with Higher Education diploma and Archivist with University diploma]. Similar problems may arise for the engineers, a large group in most countries. The following solution is proposed, whereby the Archivist is not present in the German translation, and Archivar/in, Diplom (FH) and (Uni) are not present in all other translations.

Table 4.3 Code, source list and three look-up tables for six occupational titles

Code	Source list	en_UK	de_DE	nl_NL
26210100	Archivist	Archivist	-	Archivaris
26210101	Archivist (HEd)	-	Archivar/in, Diplom (FH)	
26210102	Archivist (Uni)	-	Archivar/in, Diplom (Uni)	
21410100	Industrial engineer	Industrial engineer	Ingenieur	-
21410101	Industrial engineer (Uni)	-	-	Ingenieur (wo)
21410102	Industrial engineer (HEd)	-	-	Ingenieur (hbo)

A third issue relates to the distinction between licensed or certified and non-licensed occupations, such as the Accountant, as shown in Table 4.4. For EU-countries, the database of licensed occupations will be used to identify the licensed occupations. For non-EU-countries licensed occupations will be added if reported.

Table 4.4 Code, source list and two look-up tables for six occupational titles

Code	Source list	nl_NL	en_UK
24110100	Accountant	-	Accountant (unqualified)
24110102	Accountant (Uni)	Register-accountant (RA)	-
24110103	Accountant (chartered)	-	Accountant (chartered)
24110104	Accountant (HEd)	Accountant, administratieconsulent (AA)	-

4.9 Occupations in the corporate hierarchy

Large and medium-sized organisations usually have a well-developed division of work, shaping hierarchical demarcation lines between occupations. For several reasons, issues related to the corporate hierarchy have to be solved in the database. First, ISCO-08 has assigned different skill levels to different positions within the hierarchy. Second, respondents prefer to report their position within the hierarchy. Third, valid self-identification assumes that occupational titles are clear with respect to their position in the corporate hierarchy. Several features of the corporate hierarchy are discussed here.

Many respondents prefer to indicate the hierarchy within their occupation by adding words such as senior or junior. It requires substantive empirical work to conclude for which occupations these levels are applicable and for which they are not, and this may vary across countries. Therefore, the source list does not include separate entries for junior or senior variations of an occupational title. The same applies to respondents reporting to be the 1st, 2nd or 3rd cook, pilot, or other occupational titles, and to the word ‘all-round’. The matching algorithms will disregard these additions. In the WageIndicator websurvey respondents are offered a follow-up survey question where these categories can be ticked, if desired.

Respondents also prefer to indicate when they occupy a supervisory position. ISCO-08 classifies supervisors in the same unit group as the most skilled workers supervised, while department managers are classified in Major Group 1 Managers. For survey respondents, the boundaries between the two groups may not be too clear, valid coding requires that they are perceived to be distinct. Therefore, the database includes long lists of first line supervisors and department managers, such as:

- first line supervisor front-office tellers;
- first line supervisor office clerks;
- first line supervisor back-office clerks;
- first line supervisor police inspectors or detectives;
- first line supervisor food preparation workers;
- technical department manager;
- engineering department manager;
- manufacturing department manager;
- financial department manager;
- personnel department manager.

The coding should be tested against the answers to the firm size question and against the question about supervisory position and number of persons supervised. A set of rules will be developed to modify the respondent’s code when these tests yield unreliable combinations.

The concepts of careering, job ladders and job-enlargement blur the demarcation lines across occupations, whereas clarity is critical for valid self-identification. In the EurOccupations project this turned out most problematic for the assistant occupations (Tijdens, 2010). Is the assistant plumber part of a job ladder to become a plumber and thus one occupation, or are both separate occupations?

This will vary worldwide and therefore in the source list the word assistant has been avoided as much as possible and replaced with the word helper.

4.10 Composite jobs

Small organisations tend to employ workers in composite jobs. Respondents may therefore want to classify themselves in more than one occupation. Websurveys using search trees have two solutions to this problem. The first solution includes an instruction to the survey question that the occupation should be selected on which most time is spent. The second solution is allowing respondents to tick more than one occupation. Unfortunately, due to technical constraints the WageIndicator websurvey does not facilitate a second choice, but may do so in the years to come.

4.11 Handicraft workers and machine-operators

In the course of the 20th century, small-scale workshops have been replaced by factories and craft occupations by machine-operators due to industrialisation and technological innovations. Countries vary with respect to the degree that these processes have taken place. Nevertheless, even in highly industrialised countries traditional craft occupations continue to exist, supplying handicraft goods for commercial markets. In the source list the machine operator and the handicraft workers are assigned distinct occupational titles, e.g. the *Handicraft weaver* and the *Weaving machine operator*, or the *Handicraft leather worker* and the *Shoemaking machine operator*. For food manufacturing, the word handicraft worker is not applicable. For bakers and butchers, in most countries the occupational titles will refer primarily to retail trade and a different phrasing is used for comparable occupations in manufacturing.

4.12 Subsistence farmers, fishers, hunters and gatherers

The evidence of subsistence workers has been an issue of debate. Due to rapid urbanisation worldwide, the number of subsistence workers is likely to decrease further, although an economic crisis may well lead to a temporal increase of this group. ISCO-08 includes a sub-major group, which is detailed into the *Subsistence crop farmers*, *Subsistence livestock farmers*, *Subsistence mixed crop and livestock farmers*, and *Subsistence fishers, hunters, trappers and gatherers*. The source list includes these four occupations. For the Netherlands these occupations have been translated with the extension 'hobby', e.g. the Subsistence livestock farmer is translated to *Veehouder (hobby)*, to be distinguished from Livestock farmer (in Dutch Veehouder).

4.13 My job title is not in your list

Even with 7,000 occupational titles in a look-up table, there will be respondents who cannot identify their occupation in the semantic matching tool. This problem can be solved by making the selection of the semantic matching not mandatory. This allows respondents to key in an occupational title, not to select any of the matches and to continue the survey. For these cases, the survey holder has to undertake office coding. As these occupational titles are likely to be rare titles, the survey holder is advised to include a separate page with survey questions about the keyed in title, for example about the required educational level and the number of co-workers in the same occupation in the country, asked in broad classes. In case of very rare occupations it may be considered less necessary to code the occupation. This procedure also allows to detect new and emerging occupations. Depending on the sample size this office coding may be a time- and budget-consuming operation on the side of the survey-holder.

In case the survey question about occupation is mandatory, implying that the respondent cannot continue the survey unless an occupational title is selected, it is advised to add an extra question

asking whether respondent could identify his/her own occupational title and asking for a job description. This allows to identify unreliable answers.

5. Testing validity and reliability of occupational measurement

Once the database is implemented, a programme to test the validity and reliability of the occupational measurement should be developed. To measure the validity, the most appropriate approach would be to ask websurvey respondents twice about their occupation, first in an open-ended question and then with the semantic matching tool. To measure reliability it may be suitable to ask websurvey respondents in a web panel to identify their occupation with the semantic matching tool in two separate waves, thereby controlling for job changes or changes of employer.

Finally, the semantic matching tool not only challenges the validity and reliability of the measurement. In websurveys it is common to use additional measures of performance, such as the response times and the dropout rates at this particular question in relation to overall dropout rates. These measures should also be included in the test programme.

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InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion

Referring to the EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the general objectives of InGRID – Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘Poverty and Living Conditions’ and ‘Working Conditions and Vulnerability’ by providing transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange activities and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

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More detailed information is available on the website: www.inclusivegrowth.be

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